

New records of *Oecobius putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 from South Africa (Araneae: Oecobiidae)

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ABSTRACT: New records of the spider *Oecobius putus* O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 are provided from South Africa. The general morphology of live specimens is discussed and photographs are provided, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

Keywords: conservation, biodiversity, distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSА)

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Oecobius* Lucas, 1846 is the largest genus of the Oecobiidae, known from 89 species and a single subspecies, and has a wide geographical range (World Spider Catalogue, 2022). Several species of *Oecobius* are synanthropic and widely distributed in the world. Cosmopolitan species known from the Afrotropical Region are *O. navus* Blackwall, *O. cellariorum* Duges and *O. putus* Pickard-Cambridge (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué, 1997).

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSА) (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015), several *Oecobius* specimens were sampled but most of them belong to the cosmopolitan species *O. navus*, a species widely distributed throughout South Africa. Between the survey material, a second species, *O. putus*, described by O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876 from the Temple of Pbilse in Upper Egypt, was identified in 2010 (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2010).

The general morphology of live specimens is discussed and photographs are provided, with notes on their behaviour, distribution and conservation status.

TAXONOMY

Oecobius putus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876

Oecobius putus O. Pickard-Cambridge, 1876: 544; Dippenaar-Schoeman 2010: 558; 2014: 106; 2021: 7.

Diagnostic characteristics: Size: total length female and male 2-3 mm, with males slightly smaller than females (Fig. 4). Carapace sub-circular, wider than long, without fovea; eight eyes arranged in two rows in compact group near centre of carapace, with posterior median eyes circular or oval (Figs 1–3); pale yellow with a brown band formed of irregular brown spots at the lateral margin; ocular area dark. Sternum heart-shaped, yellowish bordered with brown; furnished with scattered long black hairs; labium is wider than long, blackish in colour with a slightly rounded tip. Abdomen more or less flattened; oval to round; slightly overlapping carapace; variable darker cruciform marking and white subcutaneous pigment granules (Fig. 3) dense covering of white setae (Fig. 1). Leg colour similar to carapace. Palp shown in Figs 5 & 6 and epigyne in Figs 7 & 8.

Figs 1–3. *Oecobius putus*: 1. Female from Bloemfontein. 2. Female from Kuruman. 3. Male from Bloemfontein (Photos 1 & 3: Rudi Steenkamp, 2. Ruan Booysen).

Figs 4–8. *Oecobius putus*: 4. Male and female from the Sandveld Nature Reserve (Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman). 5. Male palp (Charles Haddad). 6. Male palp after Kritscher (1966). 7. Epigyne (Charles Haddad). 8. Epigyne (Ansie Dippenaar-Schoeman).

Figs 9–11. *Oecobius navus*: 9. Female from Irene (Peter Webb). 10. Epigyne. 11. Palp after Lawrence (1952).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Egypt, Sudan to Iran, Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, India. Introduced to USA, Mexico (World Spider Catalogue, 2022). New: South Africa.

KNOWN DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Free State: Sandveld Nature Reserve (-27.85, 25.93); Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Northern Cape:** 39 km E of Groblers-hoop (-28.85, 22.30); Akkerendam Nature Reserve near Calvinia (-31.433, 19.783); Kuruman (-27.46, 23.43).

BEHAVIOUR

Oecobius species live in star-shaped mesh webs made over cracks, crevices and in the corners of rocks or walls. The web serves as a protective retreat while the anchor threads attached to the substrate notify the spider of approaching prey. The spider sits beneath the web on the substrate with its back facing the sheet. When prey touches a thread, the spider rushes out.

A video of *O. putus* taken by the second author shows how they rapidly circle the prey in an anti-clockwise, as well as clockwise, direction, ensnathes it in silk using the stout, curved setae of the anal tubercle to comb the silk from the large posterior spinnerets, and then drags the prey under the disk web, after which it is discarded. When disturbed, the spider runs away rapidly from the retreat into a crevice nearby. *O. putus* were found in houses, where they often prey on ants, but also on small flies, bugs, and beetles.

Oecobius putus resembles *O. navus* in size and shape but the patterns on the body differ (Fig. 9), as well as the genitalia (Figs 10 & 11). The cephalic region of *O. putus* is lighter in colour (almost colourless), and the cardiac mark on the abdomen is dark brown to black. Conversely, the cephalic region of *O. navus* is clearly darkened, and the cardiac mark is light brown.

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